

THE MECHANISM OF IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF UPBRINGING IN FUTURE TEACHERS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article discusses about the content of improving the methodical training of future primary school teachers, some tasks and pedagogical conditions for its implementation.*

Keywords: *education, methodology, creativity, communication, electronic educational resources, methodological training, technology, future teacher, recommendations.*

INTRODUCTION

By the time of graduation from a higher educational institution, future primary school teachers should have the tools of professional activity that allow them to achieve modern educational goals. The level of mastery of the future primary school teacher in achieving the tasks set by society and the state determines the level of readiness of the teacher for methodological activities and professional skills that will be formed throughout his life. In world educational and research institutions, scientific research is being conducted on the didactic and pedagogical possibilities of educational situations aimed at improving the quality and efficiency of primary education, improving its theoretical and methodological aspects, improving the model of developing the professional training of future teachers, and increasing the level of theoretical knowledge of teaching subjects among students. At the same time, special attention is being paid to improving the effectiveness of the system for training future primary school teachers, creating pedagogical and psychological opportunities aimed at organizing a process that develops future professional competencies in students.

The process of improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for teaching the subject of "Upbringing" as a continuous system consists of using communicative, electronic-information educational resources, working on oneself, developing creativity, methodological, pedagogical, organizational-methodical and results-oriented components.

The pedagogical opportunity to improve the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for teaching the subject of "Upbringing" is developed on the basis of clarifying the content of the adaptive-orientational, basic and creative-productive stages. The future primary school teacher forms and improves the initial experience of working on himself in a higher educational institution. The success of a specialist in his professional field depends on how complete and qualitatively the foundations of methodological activity are formed.

The psychological-pedagogical and social orientation of the content of pedagogical education of future primary school teachers requires a special approach.

One of the most important ways to improve the professional training of future primary school teachers is to increase the level of theoretical and practical preparation for innovative

activities at school, which includes the formation of a creative, individual style. In the process of training a primary school teacher, in our opinion, it is advisable to use the following methods:

- conducting interactive problem lectures, that is, actively using the “question-and-answer” method during the lecture;

- preparing short presentations that reveal one of the questions asked by students on the topic being studied, etc.;

- introducing such educational forms as “round table”, “seminar” during practical classes, in which students study important aspects of the specialty based on their independent developments during the discussion;

- debates, discussions, analysis of pedagogical situations, conducting lessons through video recordings;

- the use of role-playing and business games, case methods, and "brainstorming" in the school educational process that help develop the teacher's activity, creativity;

- conducting seminars, master classes, and training sessions that help form the professional competence of future primary school teachers;

- extensive use of electronic educational resources and multimedia tools in the process of conducting lectures and practical classes;

- use of elements of imitation, reflection, and relaxation in the process of individual practical classes;

- the use of new approaches that ensure their objectivity and reliability in monitoring and assessing student achievements.

In this regard, the development of students' research and creative skills in the educational process of higher education occupies a special place. It allows future teachers to form the ability to see new things in modern school theory and practice, to find non-standard solutions to the problems facing the school and bring them to the stage of implementation.

The system of organizing such work requires attention to the formation of research skills in writing course and graduation qualification works in a phased manner, as well as the study of all subjects of the curriculum, the implementation of research and creative projects, as well as the participation of students in research activities.

The problem of studying the individual characteristics of future primary school teachers and the possibilities of taking them into account in the educational process is a problem. Naturally, the management of such a system requires the development of a special program, as well as the introduction of individual programs for the personal and professional development of gifted students.

Another problem of the system of training future primary school teachers is related to the formation of students' ability to learn independently and work on themselves. One of the means of solving this problem is the development of educational and methodological complexes of subjects, electronic educational resources, which should provide a system of independent work of the student, including self-control, current and final control tasks.

Most definitions of methodological training associate a teacher's methodological training with knowledge, skills and qualifications; readiness and ability for independent methodological activity; certain personal characteristics. From our point of view, the following definition of methodological training, taking into account the professional orientation of the student, is

considered complete. Under the methodological training of a primary school teacher, we understand the integrative qualities of a person that characterize his abilities and training:

using their basic fundamental knowledge and communicative abilities in organizing the educational process in primary schools and performing pedagogical tasks;

acquiring methodological knowledge and skills in the educational process;

modeling and designing pedagogical activity through a high level of educational and professional motivation;

working on oneself, self-actualization and self-improvement in the methodology of teaching subjects in primary schools.

During professional training, a future primary school teacher must learn to solve educational tasks, starting from mastering fundamental subjects.

The motivational component characterizes the level of psychological readiness of a future primary school teacher for pedagogical activity and reflects the motives of his educational and cognitive activity and the level of interest in methodological activities.

To solve the above problems, the training of future primary school teachers is aimed at using a practice-oriented method. Methodological subjects are called subjects intended for methodological preparation for future teachers. The main result of methodological preparation is the readiness of students to teach primary school subjects, to carry out educational and developmental activities of schoolchildren through the subject and educational process, as well as to carry out scientific and research work on educational and developmental problems. The most important part of methodological preparation is the practical training of a future primary school teacher. The practical training of a teacher provides “practical mastery of the components of pedagogical activity, readiness to solve problems in real conditions of the educational process, corresponding to the direction of pedagogical education”. The psychological, pedagogical and social orientation of the content of pedagogical education of future primary school teachers requires a special approach. In the context of the modernization of higher pedagogical education, it is very promising to take into account the positive experience of professional training of primary school teachers in the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad.

CONCLUSION

Currently, improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers, along with the appropriate use of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the educational process, is closely related to international assessment programs. Today, it is important not only to provide future primary school teachers with ready-made knowledge, but also to teach them to use electronic information resources and assess students' literacy based on international assessment programs.

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